

Application Letter: Registraton and Dispatch

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Abstract:

In general administration, registration, as well as dispatches, based on registration are important, which is basically causality, when studied. Registration is a cause, where as, dispatch is it's effect or an outcome. In this paper, we shall study, about registration, dispatch, as well as procedures, in general administration.

Keywords: Public Administration, Registration, and Dispatch

Introduction:

We shall begin with two application letters, written by author for registration of his company, Mental Asylum of Education, beginning from registration of organization of same name, as per Company Act 2063, and Sanstha Darta Act 2034, of Nepal.

In this application letter, Registration number has been discussed as "Darta Number", Dispatch Number has been discussed as "Chalani Number", and "Ref" has been discussed, for application, to follow court procedures, as per laws, and as mentioned in Widhaan of Mental Asylum of Education.

In general, besides any administration, Courts too; and all administrations, would provide registration number, dispatch number, and Ref number, which would mean, numerical indexing, allowing us to cite works in administrations, same like as letters cited application, as per Chalani Number (Dispatch Number) 88.

Now let us study, about application letter, beginning from Registration Number. This application had to be registered in District Administration Office, as it is addressed. In general application, head of any office is addressed, and it depends entirely upon that office, as per it's working procedure, if head of that office would read, endorse, and register any application or not. Employees working in that office, with ranks lower then that of office do generally register application to work, as per working procedures of that administration.

I haven't used date completely in date, and have written just year and month, in date, as I was confused of date, which too is a format of application letter.

I have used word, "Chalani Number" as another additional parameter, in application letter, which would mean, after registration of application, as per contents in application letter, along with this application letter, another letter provided by District Administration Office would be needed, where as Chalani Number would still be required to be inserted in the parameter of Chalani Number section, unless, in that same application letter "Chalani Number" too is mentioned

In this letter, Dispatch number has been mentioned, as per similar work, and application letter, submitted to Department of Cottage and Small Scale Industries.

Working Procedure:

In administration; need of application letter indicates give and take which would mean, we need to submit an application letter, and based on that application letter, works are processed and done, and we are provided some response as output in form of letter.

That would be like as computing, based on input, output and processing.

Problems:

The letter, provided by Department of Small and Cottage Scale Industries would still need to be registered, in my firm, Mental Asylum of Education, as per works of registration, after completion of registration of firm.

That was case of firm, whereas in above letter, individual has been mentioned.

This letter too needed to be registered, but question arises about, how to register, as author being an individual doesn't has any firm, and that letter was in response to application letter made by author for making postal stickers more scientific. Identities provided by nation, if used, (Like as Citizenship certificate, passport, Voters ID card, Driving License, and such identities), then it would be personal, or individual method of record-keeping, as firm has been mentioned, neither is of any concern of firm.

Solutions:

In the letter provided by Postal Service, record keeping would be individual, where as in letter provided by Department of Cottage and Small Scale Industries, record keeping of letter would be based on firm, as per application of firm.

Further Problems:

Problems that does arises is, Should any certificate has to have registration number or dispatch number or both?

Generally certificates have registration number provided by any administration, and doesn't have dispatch number; which is needed, as per applications submitted, either be menioned in certificates, be provided in seperate application letter.

Our Initial Consideration:

In our earlier application letter which had, "Registration number", as well as "Dispatch number" both would be needed, in certificates, which would mean, registration number being provided by authorities, and dispatch number being provided by very same authorities, based on application letters submitted; and response to the application letter, after output of work, based on application letter.

Conditions and Arguments:

In administrations, Registration numbers and Dispatch numbers are thought as similiar, and sometimes even of equal values.

An example can be taken that, neither me, nor any fellows, would register any certificates as per their personal record keeping, then show it to peoples, when required. Book of registration (Darta Kitaab/Darta Khata) is mentioned in Laws of Nepal, which means about individual

registration.

That would mean, in Registration Book, individual registration has to be discussed, which would begin from 1, 2,

In Individual Registration, besides registration, concern of letter mentioning individual registration would be needed to study, along with how to use to certificates.

Then that would be have following consequences, for any works, based on certificates or licenses provided to us by any authorities.

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As registered in...and having record record in individual record keeping number, (Darta Kitaab/Book of Registration)....."

That would mean, regardless of places where we would submit documents, our individual record keeping would be important, relying on same registration number.

If we don't rely on individual record keeping, then, we have to assume, Registration number (Darta Number) provided by any organization, or authorities , is the Dispatch number, as per our submission of application letter, or documents to get work done.